

Temporalities in research: How to deal with 🏴‍☠️ publishing methods over time?

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1 Background

🏴‍☠️ (Ogham) stones, e.g. the Ogham stone CIIC 178 (Figure 1), are monoliths with the early medieval Primitive Irish Ogham script, mostly erected on the island of Ireland and in the western part of Britain between the 4th and 9th centuries. They are an important source for Archaic or Proto-Irish language and society. Names on the stones seem to be dedicated to a person. It remains unclear, however, whether the stones were grave markers, for example, or designated land ownership (Macalister, 1945; MacManus, 1997; Schmidt and Thiery, 2022) (Bogdani et al., 2021, pp.119-127). The inscriptions consist of names and relations (formula words) such as MAQI (🏴‍☠️; engl. son) to feature kinship or tribal relations (MacManus, 1997).

Figure 1: Ogham stone at Dunmore Head (An Dún Mór), the westernmost point on the mainland of the island of Ireland on 27.08.2022, 52°06'36.9 "N 10°28'23.5 "W, bottom left: Peter and Florian Thiery on the Ogham research trip in August 2022 [Florian Thiery and Peter Thiery, CC BY 4.0]

Ogham stones have been part of research for decades. Over time, several books, online databases and repositories comprising different numbering systems and readings of ogham inscriptions were produced. So the critical question is, “How to model research on Ogham (e.g. the readings of inscriptions) over time and different media using different sources and platforms with the help of graphs and Semantic Web technologies?”.

2 Methods and Data

This paper describes a use case from the “Linked Open Ogham Data Project” (Thiery, 2023a,b), which was set up in 2019 by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network and supported by the Wikimedia Germany Open Science Fellows Program. It uses “analogue” publications/catalogues on Ogham (Cuppige and Bennett, 1986; Macalister, 1945; MacManus, 1997; O’Sullivan and Sheehan, 1996; Ziegler, 1994), online databases/repositories such as “Ogham in 3D” or “Celtic Inscribed Stones Project” (CISP) to transform and model the data with the help of Semantic Web and graph technologies within a hybrid Ogham LOD workflow” (Thiery et al., 2021) (Figure 2), based on the idea of Open Science and the FAIR Principles as Linked Open Data (LOD) (Thiery, 2022), in Wikidata and Open Street Map (OSM). Semantic modelling and LOD techniques such as RDF and Wikidata are used to describe, e.g. the different readings of inscriptions over time (Schmidt et al., 2022).

Figure 2: The hybrid Linked Open Data Ogham Workflow. [Florian Thiery, Timo Homburg, Sophie C. Schmidt and Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons]

3 Discussion

This paper shows that using semantic modelling and LOD techniques to create a network of stones, data and individual views, e.g. readings of inscriptions, helps to model temporalities in research. For this purpose, digitalisation and LODification of books, LODification of “old fashioned” 1990s databases such as “CISP” or “TITUS ogam” as well as import data in community hubs like Wikidata or OSM is needed. Volunteers and Citizen Scientists can also help improve the data within this system.

Figure 3: Linked Open Geodata GeoSPARQL Example. [Florian Thiery and Timo Homburg, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons]

Figure 4: Linked Open Geodata Wikidata Example. [Florian Thiery and Timo Homburg, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons]

As an example: other identifiers of CIIC 178 (Macalister, 1945, p.170): CISP COUME/1, Cuppage 268 (Cuppage and Bennett, 1986), Wikidata Q106680850, OSM node 5145413640 and as LOD <http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000178>. Macalister (Macalister, 1945) read “ERC MAQI MAQI-ERCIA S MU DOVINIA”, Cuppage et al. (Cuppage and Bennett, 1986) “ERC MAQI MAQI-ERCIA S [MU] DOVINI[A]” and McManus (MacManus, 1997) “ERC MAQI MAQI-ERCIA[S MU] DOVI[N]IA”. The readings are slightly similar but contain a lot of uncertainties over time. Still, nevertheless, the mentioned names (Goidelic/male) “ERC”, “MAQI-ERCIA S”, and “DOVINIA” and relations like “MAQI” (engl. son of) are still the same. LOD and Wikidata help to model and visualise these opinions and relations as temporalities in research.

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